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Under what conditions and why is carbon pricing effective?
A realist synthesis of ex-post evidenceNiklas Döbbling-Hildebrandt^{1,2,*} , Diana Danilenko¹ , William F Lamb^{1,2} and Jan C Minx^{1,2} ¹ Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research, Berlin, Germany² Priestley Centre for Climate Futures, School of Earth and Environment, University of Leeds, Leeds, United Kingdom

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E-mail: niklas.doebbling-hildebrandt@pik-potsdam.de**Keywords:** carbon pricing, climate change mitigation, climate policy, policy evaluation, systematic review, realist synthesisSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)**Abstract**

To get on track for the rapid emissions reductions required to meet the Paris Agreement temperature goal, we need to understand what climate policies work, under what conditions, and why. In this review, we study how carbon pricing policies lead to emissions reductions and which context factors make each of these mechanisms more or less effective. We systematically review the evidence from 80 ex-post carbon pricing evaluations, covering 21 policy schemes across the globe. Using a realist synthesis methodology we collect 177 hypotheses on how and under what conditions this policy works, clustering hypotheses into nine mechanisms that explain why emission reductions were achieved. We extract 293 evidence statements from the primary studies to evaluate the relevance of each of the mechanisms across different sector and country contexts. We find that in the short term there is evidence that emissions reductions are achieved by a mix of fuel switching, efficiency improvements, downscaling of some emission-intensive activities, and leakage. The prevalence of these mechanisms varies by sector and country. For other emission reduction mechanisms identified in this study, such as low-carbon technology scaling, investments, and research and development activities, there is less robust evidence, suggesting that these need to be further evaluated through longer-term policy evaluations. To gain a rigorous understanding of what climate policies work, under what conditions, and why, we need to make best use of the emerging evidence base using evidence synthesis methods that address policy-relevant research questions.

1. Introduction

To make progress towards climate neutrality, it is increasingly important to understand why, and under what conditions climate policies work. Thousands of climate policies have been implemented to date [1–5] and some have achieved significant emissions abatement [6–9]. However, global greenhouse gas emissions are still growing steadily [10, 11] and there remains considerable debate about the most promising policy instruments.

Carbon taxes and emission trading schemes are among the most widely applied climate policy instruments [12], but there is no agreement on the

extent to which these policies can help achieve net zero emissions [13–16]. A recent meta-analysis found that—contrary to prior research [17]—carbon pricing schemes have more than marginal effects in reducing emissions [8]. However, there remain large differences in effects that cannot be explained by policy stringency alone. To inform this debate, it is critical to apply evidence synthesis methods to gain a nuanced understanding of which policies work, under what conditions, and why.

In this review, we study the mechanisms by which carbon pricing schemes deliver emissions reductions. Economic theory commonly assumes an *a priori* relationship between the application of a carbon

price and emission reductions, without explaining the causal mechanisms at play [14, 18, 19]. Empirical policy evaluations, on the other hand, find that carbon prices trigger a variety of underlying mechanisms, including, for example, fuel switching behaviour, low-carbon technology investments and adoption, or leakage [15, 20, 21]. We therefore aim to identify, structure and synthesise the evidence on these mechanisms, as a means to advancing our understanding of the conditions by which carbon pricing schemes succeed or fail.

Our review is situated in recent discussions on the application of systematic evidence synthesis methods to the climate policy literature. Vast amounts of available evidence have yet to be synthesised to effectively inform policy decisions. Recent maps of the scientific literature find more than 400 000 academic publications studying climate change [22], of which more than 80 000 specifically evaluate mitigation policies [23]. As long as all these valuable research findings remain scattered across disciplinary journals, and no attempt is made to understand whether they support or contradict each other, the ever-growing evidence base is of limited use for policy making [24]. Traditional literature reviews often fail to systematically evaluate what can be learned from the plentiful policy assessments, due to a lack of rigorous review methods [25].

Systematic reviews are starting to gain ground in the field of climate policy evaluation, but studies have mainly used quantitative meta-analysis techniques, or have focused on outcome effectiveness. To our knowledge, few have attempted to synthesise evidence on policy mechanisms. In the last year, for instance, a number of systematic reviews were published to evaluate carbon pricing policies, addressing the questions of their effectiveness [8, 26], their effect on innovation [27], health co-benefits [28], and whether they received public support [29, 30]. All of these reviews combine evidence on the same research question to derive a more robust answer to the question at hand and to uncover inconsistencies between study findings. Yet, systematic reviews can also help to answer explanatory questions, including why certain policies are effective or not.

A wide array of methods for synthesis of evidence across primary studies have evolved in other research fields [31–33]. These include configurative methods that are used to interpret and triangulate evidence across studies to answer research questions that individual primary studies do not address in isolation (see figure 1) [32]. Unlike traditional literature reviews, configurative research methods still follow rigorous and transparent synthesis methods, just like any reliable primary study would do.

This study is the first to apply a *realist synthesis* methodology to study climate policy. We review the evidence on carbon pricing to assess under what conditions and why the policy is able to reduce emissions. Previous studies have explored the applicability of the method for the assessment of climate change adaptation [34] and provided the first applications to adaptation practices [35, 36]. In the context of climate change mitigation, Barletti *et al* [37] use realist synthesis to study community engagement practices in the land-use sector. In addition, a number of studies have applied realist synthesis to study health outcomes of energy efficiency interventions in household heating [38–40]. In this study, we refine and adopt the method to synthesise the evidence from climate policy evaluations. We thus showcase the benefits of the method for learning from policy experience in this field.

In this article we aim to compile evidence based theories on the working mechanisms of carbon pricing across sectors and schemes. We use a *realist synthesis* methodology to answer three interrelated research questions: (1) What are the hypothesised mechanisms by which carbon pricing schemes are effective? (2) What is the role of different contexts in moderating these mechanisms? (3) What is the underlying evidence supporting these hypotheses? Our dataset is a compilation of 80 carbon pricing evaluations obtained through a systematic literature search and screening process. From this we extract 177 hypotheses on how and under what conditions the policy works and synthesise these into nine main hypotheses. Based on 293 pieces of evidence on 21 carbon pricing schemes, we test and refine the theories as a foundation for a more faceted understanding of how carbon pricing leads to emissions reductions.

2. Realist synthesis

Realist synthesis is a systematic review method designed to move beyond the question of ‘what works?’ and to study the causal links between the policy and its outcomes. While the identification of causal mechanisms is a common form of empirical analysis [41, 42], systematic reviews are traditionally more focussed on the aggregation of the ultimate outcome of a policy. Realist synthesis, on the other hand, addresses the question of which actors are supposed to react to a policy, in which way, and what the pre-conditions are to achieving these reactions, by building on quantitative and qualitative lines of evidence [43, 44].

What are the mechanisms triggered by the policy that lead to the outcome? Where are the potential blockages that prevent the mechanism from unfolding? And how do different contextual settings alter the causal linkages? Realist synthesis aims to answer these questions by systematically searching for and evaluating available evidence.

The synthesis is guided by the development and testing of hypotheses and theories. In the realist framework these are expressed as context-mechanism-outcome (CMO) configurations, as depicted in figure 2. In a given context C, the policy triggers a mechanism M, which leads to an outcome O [44, 45]. As an example, an increase in vehicle fuel duty could trigger private car owners living in urban areas (C) to increase their usage of public transport and active travel (M), leading to reduced household emissions (O). Often combinations or sequences of mechanisms need to be triggered to cause an outcome [43]. Realist synthesis aims to collect and synthesise theories on the mechanisms and context factors leading from a policy intervention to its outcome(s). These should be specified as a testable hypothesis for the further investigation [46].

The collected hypotheses are tested against the best available evidence, identified through systematic and transparent literature searches. Unlike other synthesis methods (e.g. meta-analysis), realist synthesis is not restricted to evidence in predefined formats [43]. Instead, it triangulates heterogeneous evidence to test the validity of a theory. The reviewed evidence may also suggest amendments to the theory, for instance, where conflicting findings point towards relevant, previously unconsidered, context factors that may explain why a mechanism was triggered in some but not all reviewed cases. In this way, realist synthesis aims to refine our understanding of a policy rather than quantifying or ranking the relevance of different mechanisms [43, 47].

Realist synthesis follows an iterative approach of searching for hypotheses and testing these against the available evidence, with the aim of validating and refining theory [43]. The broad questions asked by realist syntheses open the floor for a wide range of potential theories, combined with the appreciation of various forms of evidence, this could lead to infinite iterations of refining and testing hypotheses. Realist synthesis will therefore not be able to review relevant evidence exhaustively [44]. While this distinguishes this method from more aggregative reviews that study more narrow research questions and aim to capture all relevant evidence [32], it does not relieve the reviewer from a transparent and rigorous assessment of the primary evidence [43, 47].

3. Methods

Given the observed differences in the effectiveness of carbon pricing schemes across the globe [8], we use realist synthesis to develop a theory of change around carbon pricing effectiveness. Carbon pricing is commonly advocated for its simplicity. It charges a uniform price for the emission of each ton of carbon dioxide or its equivalents—ideally across sectors. Its core assumption is that policy makers do not need to worry about the specific mechanisms (where and how

Figure 2. Context-mechanism-outcome framework: realist synthesis aims to unpack the black box, between the implementation of an intervention and its outcomes. This is conceptualised in a framework, considering contexts and mechanisms relevant to cause a given outcome [43].

emissions can best be reduced), but that all emitters are incentivised to reduce emissions to avoid the cost [14, 48]. We aim to refine this theory by studying the mechanisms to gain a better understanding on what it is about the policy that makes it more or less effective in different contexts.

We synthesise the evidence from a set of primary ex-post policy evaluations studying the causal impact of carbon pricing on emissions. We choose to review causal ex-post policy evaluations for two reasons. First, all reviewed studies assess a carbon pricing intervention and an emissions outcome. And secondly, studies applying causal inference methods on non-experimental data commonly engage intensively with the data to ensure their finding is not an artefact of any confounding factor, providing valuable information on mechanisms and contexts in the form of auxiliary assessments or the collection of supplementary data.

The realist synthesis is performed as a hand-based review method, except for the literature screening, which is supported by machine-learning techniques.

The systematic search and selection of studies for this review were performed collectively with the previously published quantitative systematic review [8]. We search four bibliographic databases (Web of Science, Scopus, JSTOR, RePEc) and Google Scholar (see figure 3). The search and computer-assisted screening method are described in the supplementary material. We identify 80 relevant studies that fulfil our inclusion criteria. A list of the relevant studies can be found in supplementary table S2.

The data extraction for our realist synthesis is conducted independently of the data that was extracted for the meta-analysis [8] due to the different data requirements and methods of this study.

We inductively extract hypotheses on the working mechanisms of carbon pricing from the identified literature. We use the CMO structure as a framework and code hypotheses and evidence on contexts and mechanisms from each study. We develop the codes used to classify a specific context or mechanism iteratively while coding. The coding is conducted using the MAXQDA software. More details on

the data extraction strategy are provided in the supplementary material. The collected data is published online [49].

To synthesise the extracted data, we assess the labelled information—category by category—to identify common themes. We start by reviewing the identified hypotheses clustered by the assigned mechanism and context labels. We group the hypotheses extracted from the primary studies based on the mechanism they relate to. We also tested an alternative grouping based on the context categories, but found that the mechanism structure provided a more consistent framework for the synthesis.

For each group of hypotheses we formulate a main hypothesis describing the assumed mechanism. We then synthesise the hypotheses in each group to collect all assumptions how the mechanism is expected to unfold. In particular, we capture the context factors assumed to be relevant to explain the occurrence and intensity of a given mechanism. This is guided by the context labels assigned to each hypothesis extracted from the primary studies. The level of detail provided for the context factors ranges from broad assumptions on sector differences to much more detailed assumptions what it is about a sector, firm, or household that influences whether a mechanism is triggered.

For each of the synthesised hypotheses we assess the availability of evidence to evaluate the hypothesis. We use the labels assigned during the data extraction to identify evidence relevant to each hypothesis. Evidence, in realist synthesis, can be qualitative or quantitative, causal or descriptive. There are no genuine hierarchies assumed between different forms of evidence [43, 45]. Instead the synthesis evaluates whether different lines of evidence support or contradict each other. For contradicting evidence we attempt to identify contextual differences that could potentially explain the heterogeneous responses to the policy.

Our assessment evaluates the evidence from the 80 relevant studies identified for this review. The depth of our analysis is therefore constrained by the availability of evidence for each of the

mechanisms. For some mechanisms there is more nuanced evidence available to assess context variations in more detail than for other mechanisms, where such detailed evidence is missing.

The largest part of the extracted evidence is derived using statistical hypothesis testing, often implemented as difference-in-differences designs. We evaluate such evidence in line with the reported significance test. Insignificant findings are interpreted as *no evidence*. For other types of evidence, i.e. evidence from descriptive assessments of data, we report how the evidence was derived and generally interpret it as suggestive evidence. While we do not conduct a comprehensive risk of bias assessment, we critically evaluate the reliability of the cited evidence and report

caveats as required. We also report any caveats in the interpretation of the evidence, where the reviewed evidence is indicative of a mechanism without sufficiently establishing causality of the mechanisms to achieve the outcome.

We report our findings in the results section below, structured by the mechanisms. For each mechanism, we first provide the synthesised hypothesis, highlighting relevant details of expected variations based on the context. We continue by reporting on the evidence used to test the hypothesis, assessing to what degree the evidence supports the hypothesis. This is followed, for each mechanism, by a conclusion, which refines the hypothesis based on the assessed evidence.

4. Results

Our comprehensive machine-learning assisted screening reveals 80 relevant studies, covering 21 carbon pricing schemes across four continents. The studied policies were introduced between 1990 and 2015 on sub-national, national or regional level (see table 1) and collectively cover about 7% of global emissions in 2023 [50]. The majority of the reviewed schemes are implemented as emissions trading schemes (ETs), with only four carbon tax schemes. Table 1 shows the considerable differences between the prices charged for each ton of CO₂ equivalent, the shares of territorial emissions covered, and the sectors targeted by each policy. The Chinese ETs pilots, Quebec ETs, regional greenhouse gas initiative (RGGI) and the Finnish carbon tax show prices below US\$ 10, while for other schemes, like the Swedish carbon tax and the ETs in Tokyo and Saitama, the prices go above US\$ 100. The share of covered emissions ranges from 11% to 77% of all greenhouse gases emitted within the jurisdiction and there is considerable heterogeneity in the composition of sectors governed by the carbon price.

The heterogeneity in policy design, carbon price level, sector coverage, and country context provide a versatile source of real world policy experiences. A systematic assessment and comparison of the mechanisms triggered by these policies can inform policymakers and future research by synthesising the available evidence. The generalisability and attribution of findings to specific context factors needs to consider the multifaceted and interrelated differences between the policy schemes.

The reviewed studies largely focus on the first few years after the policy implementation and are mostly conducted using difference-in-difference designs. The reviewed policy evaluations study the policy for periods of one to 16 years of its implementation, with 80% of the studies assessing 7 years or less, thus focussing on short-run rather than long-term mechanisms. The mean price level across the studies is at about US\$ 19 per ton of emitted CO₂ equivalent.

The reviewed studies find consistent evidence that the carbon pricing policies cause emissions reductions. As shown in Döbbling-Hildebrandt *et al* [8], a meta-analysis across the 80 primary studies finds significant emissions reductions for 17 out of the 21 reviewed carbon pricing schemes. Emissions reduction effects range between -5% and -21%, indicating that emissions in an average year after the policy implementation are 5%–21% lower than they would have been in the absence of the policy. A meta-regression analysis shows significant differences in the effectiveness between the policy schemes in different

jurisdictions. The quantitative meta-analysis, however, is unable to explain the causes of this heterogeneity. In this study, we therefore evaluate complimentary evidence to study, what it is about the policy and its context that makes it more or less effective.

From 80 studies we extract 177 instances where hypotheses are mentioned, which we cluster by the nine main mechanisms (see figure 3). We evaluate these hypotheses based on the evidence provided in the same 80 studies—namely, a set of 293 statements. Most of the evidence comes from quantitative quasi-experimental research methods, namely difference-in-differences and regression discontinuity designs, and provides causal assessments of the hypotheses. However, it also includes evidence from surveys and descriptive assessments of data. We review the evidence across mechanisms and contexts to study how and under what conditions carbon pricing is able to cause emissions reductions.

The synthesis of the captured hypotheses reveals seven commonly mentioned emission reduction mechanisms. These are fuel switching, adoption of low carbon technologies, efficiency improvements, investment changes, research and development, reduced production and consumption, and leakage. In addition to the seven emission reduction mechanisms, we also identify two cognitive mechanisms which can be assumed to act as a link between the application of the policy and the trigger of emission reduction mechanisms. This results in a total of nine mechanisms reviewed here (see figure 4). 22 mentions of hypotheses expressed in primary studies could not be captured, as they could not be allocated to a specific mechanism. These are provided in Supplementary table S4. We here review the nine mechanisms separately, while interactions of the mechanisms, particularly between cognitive and emission reduction mechanisms, should be assumed.

The mechanism contexts expressed in each hypotheses 4.1.1–4.2.2 are mainly related to the policy scheme, capturing both the country of implementation and the policy design, and the studied sector. Figure 5 shows an uneven distribution of contexts, for which each of the mechanisms is evaluated in the reviewed evidence. The carbon pricing schemes covered by the reviewed evidence are summarised in table 1. The sectoral context is synthesised using the IPCC emission sectors: energy, industry, buildings, and transport (with other emission sectors not being assessed in the reviewed evidence) [52].

An overview of the hypotheses and the associated evidence is provided in table 2. The overview also points to gaps in the evidence for certain context-mechanism configurations.

Table 1. Carbon pricing schemes covered in the review: The information on introduction date, sector coverage, emissions coverage, and mean price was retrieved from the World Bank [50], except for the price data for the EU ETS, which is retrieved from ICAP [51]. The information for the sector coverage was simplified. For more detailed information on the coverage, including covered or exempted subsectors, the reader is referred to the World Bank data. Emission coverage is the share of a jurisdictions emissions covered by the carbon price in 2022. Mean prices are unweighted average prices in constant 2010 US\$ during the period analysed by the studies in our sample. The average emissions reduction effects were estimated in Döbbling-Hildebrandt [8] and are provided together with a 95% confidence interval. Where confidence intervals are not symmetric, this is an artefact from rounding. The sum of the number of studies exceeds the number of reviewed articles, as some articles study more than one policy. The effects of the eight Chinese pilot ETS schemes are often analysed collectively in a single study, while some studies focus on individual schemes. We only list pilots that have been studied individually. The Australian carbon tax was revoked in 2014.

Policy	Jurisdiction	Introduction	Sector coverage	Emissions coverage	Mean price	Achieved emissions reductions	Studies
Chinese pilot ETS						−13% [−15%; −11%]	35
o/w Hubei pilot ETS	Hubei, China	2014	Industry	27%	\$3		4
o/w Beijing pilot ETS	Beijing, China	2013	Industry, power, transport and buildings	24%	\$8		2
o/w Shanghai pilot ETS	Shanghai, China	2013	Industry, buildings, transport	36%	\$4		2
o/w Guangdong pilot ETS	Guangdong, China	2013	Industry, aviation	40%	\$5		2
o/w Shenzhen pilot ETS	Shenzhen, China	2013	Industry, power, buildings, transport	30%	\$7		1
o/w Tianjin pilot ETS	Tianjin, China	2013	Industry, buildings	35%	\$4		2
EU ETS	30 European countries	2005	Power, manufacturing industry, aviation	38%	\$20	−7% [−11%; −4%]	13
Swedish carbon tax	Sweden	1991	Transport, buildings	40%	\$103	−10% [−18%; −2%]	2
BC carbon tax	British Columbia, Canada	2008	industry, power, transport and buildings	70%	\$18	−5% [−10%; −1%]	6
Saitama ETS	Saitama, Japan	2011	Industry, power, buildings	17%	\$108	−6% [−13%; 1%]	
Tokyo ETS	Tokyo, Japan	2010	Industry, power, buildings	20%	\$106	−7% [−14%; −1%]	4
Quebec ETS	Quebec, Canada	2013	Industry, power, transport and buildings	77%	\$9	−9% [−16%; −1%]	2
RGGI	11 northeastern US states	2009	Power	14%	\$3	−21% [−28%; −14%]	5
UK carbon price support	United Kingdom	2013	Power	24%	\$22	−10% [−17%; −3%]	4
Finnish carbon tax	Finland	1990	Industry, transport, buildings	36%	\$6	−15% [−25%; −5%]	2
Swiss ETS	Switzerland	2008	Industry, power	11%	\$18	14% [−10%; 38%]	1
Australian carbon tax	Australia	2012*	Industry, power	60%	\$24	0% [−11%; 12%]	1
California CaT	California, USA	2012	Industry, power, transport, buildings	74%	\$12	−19% [−29%; −9%]	2
Korea ETS	Korea	2015	Industry, power, buildings, domestic aviation, public sector, waste sector	74%	\$15	−3% [−16%; 9%]	1

Figure 4. Synthesis of hypotheses on nine mechanisms across contexts: We group the identified hypotheses by the nine mechanisms by which carbon pricing is assumed to cause emissions reductions. The occurrence of these mechanisms depends on the context in the given sector and jurisdiction. The depiction of the context factors is simplified here and the details are provided in sections 4.1.1–4.2.2.

	Country / Region	Sector	Price level
Fuel switching			€ €
Low-carbon technology adoption			€ €
Efficiency improvements			€ €
Investments			€ €
Research and development			€
Reduced production/consumption			€ €
Leakage			€ €
Attention			€
Anticipation			€

Energy

Industry

Buildings

Transport

€ Low prices (≤US\$ 30)

€ High prices (>US\$ 30)

Figure 5. Mechanisms and the context they are evaluated in: the evidence evaluated here is distributed unevenly across the nine mechanisms. While *fuel switching*, for example, is evaluated in eight countries/regions and four emission sectors, the available evidence for *research and development* is limited to studies on China without sector-specific evaluations. The figure summarises three main dimensions of the variation in contexts, while more detailed context information is analysed in the assessment. The figure reports the presence of at least one study with a context characteristic for a given sector, without showing the share of studies with this characteristic. Six mechanisms, for instance, are studied by at least one study in a high carbon price environment, while low carbon price studies are generally overrepresented.

4.1. Emission reduction mechanisms

4.1.1. Hypothesis: emissions are reduced by switching from high emitting fuels to lower emitting fuels

A common hypothesis, expressed in many of the reviewed articles, is that individuals or firms would respond to a carbon price by switching fuels [53, 54, 57, 59, 63, 72, 83, 84, 86, 106–108]. The amount of

GHGs emitted by the combustion of fossil fuels varies by fuel. In particular, coal is significantly more emission intensive than natural gas [53, 54, 59], oil can be placed somewhere between these two fuels [59], considering their global warming potential over 100 years. Therefore, carbon prices may induce firms to switch from fossil fuels with a higher emissions

Table 2. Mechanisms through which carbon pricing is assumed to cause emissions reductions: Summary of hypothesised mechanisms and reviewed evidence.

Mechanism	Explanation	Context	Evidence				
			Energy	Industry	Transport	Buildings	Across sectors
Fuel switching	Carbon pricing induces actors to substitute high emitting fuels for lower emitting fuels	Dependent on substitutable fuels and processes; Dependent on available capacities (in the short-term)	Coal to gas transitions observed in the UK power sector [53–56]; No absolute (potentially relative) fuel switching observed for EU ETS [54] or RGGI [57–59]	Not observed for Tokyo or Saitama ETS [60] or EU ETS [61–63]	Indications from Sweden and Finland for switching from gasoline to diesel cars [64, 65]	Indications from Sweden for switching from oil heating to wood, electricity, and district heating [66]	Relative rather than absolute fuel switching caused by Chinese ETS pilots [67–75]
Low-carbon technology adoption	Carbon pricing induces actors to substitute fossil fuels for renewable and low-carbon sources (e.g. wind, solar, hydro, nuclear-power, electricity)	Dependent on availability and feasibility of low-carbon technologies	No uptake in renewable energies in Tokyo [60] and RGGI states [58]; UK carbon price increased hydro but not nuclear power [53]			Indications for increase in heat pump installations in Sweden [66]	
Efficiency improvements	Carbon pricing induces actors to adjust processes, to lower the emission intensity of their production	Dependent on costs for efficiency improvements (vary by sector and firm)	Increase in emission intensity observed in RGGI states [58]	EU ETS caused significant reductions in emission intensity in France [61, 63], Germany [62], and Lithuania [76], but not in Norway [77]			Chinese ETS pilots cause significant reductions in emission intensity [71, 73, 75, 78–80] (few studies find no such effect [81, 82]); emission intensity reductions vary by ETS pilot scheme [71]; both energy intensity [78, 79, 83] and emission intensity of energy reduced [75]; Emission intensity reductions observed in Quebec [84]

(Continued.)

Table 2. (Continued.)

Mechanism	Explanation	Context	Evidence				
			Energy	Industry	Transport	Buildings	Across sectors
Investments	Carbon pricing incentivises actors to invest into new equipment to reduce emissions	Dependent on long-term carbon price expectations and financing conditions		EU ETS fosters investments of French manufacturing sector into reduced emission intensity [63]		Indication for increased investments into heat pumps fostered by Swedish carbon tax [66]	Chinese ETS pilots reverse effect of foreign direct investment from increasing to decreasing effect on emissions [85]
Research and development	Carbon pricing fosters research and development of new technologies to reduce emissions						Chinese ETS pilots increase expenditure for research and development [86] (another study does not find the same effect [67]); number of patents [69] and of ‘green’ patents [74]; increased innovation is found to reduce emissions [69, 70]
Reduced production/consumption	Emissions can be avoided by reducing the production or consumption	Dependent on price elasticity of supply and demand	Reduced energy generation caused by Chinese ETS pilots [68, 75, 79, 83] but not by Tokyo ETS [87]	No reductions of industrial output found for Chinese ETS pilots [88, 89] or EU ETS [62]	Reductions in short-haul flights (EU ETS) [90] and urban car use (British Columbia carbon tax) [91]		No evidence for reduced production caused by Chinese ETS pilots [71, 75, 88, 89, 92], British Columbia carbon tax [93], or European carbon taxes [94]

(Continued.)

Table 2. (Continued.)

Mechanism	Explanation	Context	Evidence					
			Energy	Industry	Transport	Buildings	Across sectors	
Leakage	Production and associated emissions are relocated to jurisdictions where they are not subject to the policy or reallocated to entities that are exempted from the policy	Dependent on spare production capacities outside the treated jurisdiction and transport/transmission capacities	RGGI and UK carbon price support cause increase in (lower emission) energy imports [53, 57–59]; No evidence for increased energy imports caused by Chinese ETS pilots [68]	Within firm reallocation of production to other jurisdictions found for Californian cap-and-trade scheme [95]; No evidence for reallocation to exempted firms by EU ETS [61, 62]				No evidence for leakage caused by Chinese ETS pilots [67, 96]; Positive spill-over effects caused by Tokyo and Saitama ETS [97]
Attention	The policy response depends on the attention the policy attracts		Possibility to sell emission allowances reduces emissions less than need to purchase allowances (EU ETS) [98]	Possibility to sell emission allowances reduces emissions less than need to purchase allowances (EU ETS) [99]	British Columbia carbon tax induces larger emissions response than market induced price changes [91, 100]	British Columbia carbon tax induces larger emissions response than market induced price changes [101]	Cross-country study finds introduction effect regardless of the carbon price level [102]	
Anticipation	Emissions reductions depend on anticipated emission costs		RGGI caused emissions reductions already before its implementation [103]	EU ETS caused emissions reductions already before its implementation [62]	Downward adjustments of future carbon taxes lowered emissions reduction efforts in British Columbia [104, 105]		Chinese ETS pilots not found to cause emissions reductions between announcement and implementation [75, 96]	

intensity to fuels with lower emissions intensities. (Switching from fossil fuels to low-emission alternatives is captured in hypothesis 4.1.2 below.)

Different sectors may have varying potentials for fuel switching, depending on the type of fuel used and the availability of alternatives in the short- and in the long-run. Particularly the power sector is commonly characterised by capacities that exceed the power demand most of the time. If these capacities are made-up of power plants using different fuels, a switch in utilised fuels is feasible in the short-run [53, 54, 106, 108, 109]. In the transport [53, 110] and buildings [101] sectors, on the other hand, users are commonly bound to a specific fuel for the lifetime of their vehicles and heating installations, which may only be substituted over a longer period of time. For the manufacturing sector, there are conflicting expectations as to whether fuel switching is feasible in the short-run [84, 106], likely related to the variety of technologies used in the sector.

Evidence: Evidence for fuel switching is only found for the energy sector in the UK, subject to the carbon price support [53–56], replacing coal with natural gas combustion. The EU ETS and RGGI, instead of replacing coal by gas, are found to reduce coal combustion in the energy sector without an uptake in the combustion of other fuels [54, 57–59]. Consistent evidence for the UK carbon price support shows that the policy caused a significant decrease in emissions from coal power generation, while emissions from natural gas power plants increased at a lower magnitude [53–56]. In fact, a few years after the introduction of the carbon price support the share of coal in the energy production was lowered from 39% (2012) to 2.4% (2019), with the carbon price ranging between US\$ 30 and 40 in 2019 [53]. Evidence for the RGGI Chan and Morrow [57, 58], Yan [59] consistently shows that the carbon price reduced emissions from coal power generation, but did not increase emissions from natural gas power generation. The same effect is found for the EU ETS by a study on the German energy sector [54].

Fewer studies are available for the industry sector, while the transport and buildings sectors are only covered by descriptive evidence. The industry sectors covered by the ETSs in the EU and Japan show evidence for relative fuel switching. The EU ETS is found to cause significant reductions in the emissions from coal combustion during the second phase of the ETS policy, while no switch to natural gas or oil is detected [61–63]. Yajim *et al* [60] find no evidence for fuel switching caused by the Tokyo or Saitama ETS in the industry sector. Descriptive evidence from Sweden and Finland points into the direction that the carbon taxes also in the buildings and transport sectors led to fuel switching. In Sweden, the combustion of oil heating in households declined,

while heating with wood, electricity or district heating increased [66]. A similar trend is observed in the transport sector, where the share of diesel cars compared to gasoline cars in Sweden increased substantially between 1991 and 2015 [64], while in Finland the consumption of diesel increased and the gasoline consumption dropped [65]. While the Swedish carbon tax was introduced with a price level of US\$ 30, for Finland, this trend was observed starting at carbon prices below US\$ 10.

The evidence for the Chinese ETS pilots is not sector specific, but provides evidence for relative rather than absolute fuel switching across sectors. The policy is found to reduce coal combustion, both in absolute terms [67, 68] and as a relative share in the energy mix [69–73]. There is less evidence available to test whether coal combustion was replaced by the combustion of other fuels. An increase in the relative share of natural gas combustion is detected [74, 75], but no absolute uptake of natural gas combustion [67]. When including also other energy sources (hydro, nuclear, wind and natural gas), the ETSs are found to cause an increased energy generation from these sources [68]. The causality between the ETS pilots and reduced coal combustion should be treated with some caution, as other Chinese regions, with high GDP per capita, are found to reduce coal combustion around the same time as the ETS pilots were introduced [67].

Some more detailed evidence from the energy sector, provides further insights into the preconditions for the fuel switching mechanism. Gugler *et al* [54] calculate the marginal costs of each power plant at different carbon price levels to examine the ‘power supply structure (called the ‘merit order’)’. They show that a carbon price of 25 EUR reverses the supply structure, such that enough gas power plants supply electricity at lower marginal costs than coal power plants to satisfy the entire electricity demand at commonly observed demand levels. A similar effect is not found for the German energy sector, where the carbon price of the EU ETS was too low (until 2018) to cause substantial fuel switching between coal and natural gas. For the RGGI states, fuel switching is only observed in periods of low natural gas prices, indicating that the carbon price is unable to reverse the merit order in periods of high natural gas prices [58]. The merit order is of lower importance in highly regulated or monopolised energy markets. Cao *et al* [68] points out that electricity generation in China is based on quotas allocated without consideration of the generation costs, questioning the viability of fuel switching between facilities. And Leslie [109] shows, based on evidence for the Australian ETS, that large power producers, which run both coal and gas power plants and possess sufficient market power, may have an incentive to continue running coal power plants instead of switching to natural gas power generation and thus

obstruct the market mechanism from causing a fuel switch.

Conclusions: Emissions are reduced by switching from high emitting fuels to lower emitting fuels, under the condition that lower emission technologies are available and able to substitute previous processes. A further condition is that the carbon price is high enough to reverse the marginal costs of different fuels in favour of the lower emitting fuel. These conditions are mainly met in the energy sector, while other sectors show little evidence for fuel switching in the short run. Relatively, carbon pricing is found to reduce the share of high emitting fuels across sectors and schemes. The reviewed studies largely focus on the first few years after a policy is introduced. There are some indications that over longer time periods some durable technologies are also replaced in favour of technologies using lower emitting fuels. The evidence from the UK suggests that substantial emissions reductions can be achieved via fuel switching already at moderate carbon prices.

4.1.2. Hypothesis: low-carbon technologies are adopted to reduce GHG emissions

Carbon pricing may not only motivate the switch from one fossil fuel to another, but also incentivise the adoption of other energy sources, such as wind, solar, hydro or nuclear, or in demand-sectors the electrification of key processes [53, 72, 78, 86]. This mechanism is assumed to be a gradual transition [72], as the installed low-carbon technologies in the power sector are expected to run at (close to) full capacities even without the carbon pricing policy [53]. The mechanism, therefore requires the installation of new capacities.

Evidence: Evidence for this mechanism is limited to the energy and buildings sectors. Yajima *et al* [60] find no significant effect of the Tokyo ETS on the energy produced from renewable sources. RGGI has not caused an increase in the energy produced by renewable energies, in fact the uptake of renewable energies in the RGGI states was significantly slower as compared to other US states that did not apply a carbon price [58]. When the UK carbon price support was introduced, the hydro power has partly filled the gap of reduced fossil energy production (roughly 15%) [53]. For nuclear power Gugler *et al* [53] find no significant uptake related to the UK carbon price support. For the buildings sector, Runst and Thonipara [66] provide descriptive statistics that around the same time when carbon taxes were increased, the sale of heat pumps more than doubled, without assessing the causal impact of the tax increase on the uptake of the technology nor its causal impact on emissions.

Conclusions: The reviewed studies provide limited evidence of carbon pricing reducing emissions via the

adoption of low carbon technologies. This might be related to the type of evidence reviewed. Most studies in our sample assess the effectiveness of the policy across a rather short period of time. As expressed in the hypothesis, this mechanism is likely to take some time to unfold. Further evidence to test this hypothesis can be expected to become available the longer the policies are in place. Another explanation could be the rather low carbon prices observed for many schemes in the primary studies, reducing the profitability of the adoption of new technologies. The limited amount of evidence does not allow to identify specific contextual factors that would make this mechanism more or less relevant.

4.1.3. Hypothesis: emissions are reduced via efficiency improvements

Many study authors express hypotheses that carbon pricing may reduce emissions by lowering the emissions per unit of output [59, 62, 63, 70, 77, 80, 88, 106]. This may be achieved via reductions in energy intensity [70, 80, 106], reduced emission intensity of energy [75], or shifts in the economy towards industries with lower emission intensity [69]. Energy intensity could, for example, be achieved by 'switching to a combined heat and power system' [59] or more generally by making 'more efficient use of process heat' [62]. Reductions in the emission intensity of energy are closely linked to the mechanisms discussed above to switch to lower emitting input fuels or to replace fossil fuels by low-emission technologies such as renewable energies.

In the reviewed studies the emission intensity mechanism is described for the industry [62, 106] and energy [59] sectors. It is not excluded that the same mechanism could also be relevant in other sectors. As the reduction of emission intensity is expected to require investments [77], this mechanism is expected to require some time to unfold [59]. As the costs may differ by sector or firm, improvements in the emission intensity are expected to happen where the abatement costs are lowest [106], while in other sectors the abatement costs may be too high to observe any reductions in the emission intensity [90]. Also the size of the emitting facilities may have an impact on whether the emission intensity is reduced, as larger firms may have the advantage of scale effects so that an improvement in the processes may lead to larger emission savings and larger avoided payments for the carbon price [99].

Evidence: Evidence suggests that the ETSs in the EU, China, and Quebec caused significant reductions in the emission intensity of output. For the EU ETS this is particularly studied for the industry sector, while the policies in China and Quebec are studied across sectors. For the EU ETS, consistent evidence for reduced emission intensity is found for the manufacturing sectors in France [61, 63], Germany [62],

and Lithuania [76]. Evidence for all three countries shows significant reductions during the second phase of the ETS policy. Only in the Norwegian manufacturing sector, the EU ETS is not found to cause significant improvements of the emission intensity [77], while there is a lack of evidence for other EU countries. Studies on the Chinese ETS pilots, conducted across sectors, largely agree that the policy achieved significant reductions in emission intensity [71, 73, 75, 78–80], while a few studies do not find significant improvements of the emission intensity [81, 82]. Qi *et al* [71] study the emission intensity effect per ETS pilot and find significant emission intensity reductions only for Beijing and Hubei, while they do not find significant effects for Tianjin, Shanghai or Guangdong. The Quebec ETS in Canada is also found to significantly decrease the emission intensity [84]. Only for the RGGI, the evidence suggests an increase in the emission intensity in the power sector, likely caused by a utilisation rate below the capacity of each plant [58]. We are unable to clarify, whether the few studies not identifying a reduction in emission intensity incentivised by the EU and Chinese ETSs [77, 81, 82] fail to identify an existing effect for methodological reasons or whether they point to yet unidentified contextual factors suppressing this mechanism.

There is less evidence available to test whether this reduced emission intensity of output is explained by reduced energy intensity, reduced emission intensity of energy, or both. There are four studies testing the effect of the Chinese ETS pilots on energy intensity. Three find evidence for reduced energy intensity [78, 79, 83] and one finds an insignificant reduction effect [75]. The findings still show a limited consistency, with estimated reduction effects ranging from 1% to 39%. Cui *et al* [75] furthermore finds a significant reduction in carbon intensity of energy caused by the ETS pilots.

Firm level evidence reveals that carbon intensive plants are more responsive to the policy and that firms react by improving efficiency or shutting down of their facilities. Kim and Bae [106] find a differentiated response to the ETS implementation by Korean manufacturing firms. They use the fact that almost half of the manufacturing firms before the policy implementation were certified for their environmental performance, while the other half did not hold such a certificate. The ETS implementation caused significantly higher emission reductions among firms without environmental certification compared to certified firms. This suggests that firms with a worse environmental performance before the policy implementation follow the best practices of those firms that had reduced emissions before the policy was in place. In the EU, firms are found to increase their investments into technology to reduce emission intensity [63] (further discussed in section 4.1.4). The carbon price in the UK is found to cause the shut down of the most emission intensive plants first, while later

increases of the carbon price had relatively smaller reduction effects, as only more efficient power plants remained on the market [53]. The findings by Leroutier [55] further suggest that the UK carbon price support inhibited the entrance of high emitting plants to the UK energy sector.

Conclusions: The reviewed evidence supports the hypothesis that carbon prices achieve emissions reductions via efficiency improvements. The evidence is most comprehensive for reductions in the emission intensity of output, while only providing suggestive evidence that both energy intensity and emission intensity of energy are reduced. Sector specific evidence is mainly available for the industry sector, not allowing for a comprehensive comparison of contextual factors across sectors. The findings suggest that across a number of jurisdictions, industrial firms had unrealised potentials for efficiency improvements and carbon pricing increases the incentive to leverage these potentials. Firm level evidence suggests that most significant reactions to the policy are observed for plants with high emission intensities, which are driven to improve their efficiency or pushed out of the market. This mechanism could be studied in further detail to understand what actions firms are taking to reduce emission intensities, how these are motivated by the carbon price, and which industrial sectors are most responsive to the policy. As we did not identify any evidence for this mechanism in the buildings and transport sectors, further research is required to understand whether private households would also react to the policy by retrofitting or the purchase of more efficient appliances.

4.1.4. Hypothesis: carbon pricing fosters investments

The above presented mechanisms often require investments into updating or purchasing of equipment [77, 84, 85, 111], such as machines [77], heating systems [66] or vehicles [105]. Carbon prices may be taken into account for investment decisions as they have a direct influence on the profitability of different technologies over their lifetime. Investment decisions further depend on the availability and knowledge about affordable technical solutions [77] as well as the financing conditions for the investor [95, 111]. The mechanism is expected to reduce emissions in the long- rather than the short-run, as the translation of investment decisions into emissions reductions takes time [66, 77].

Evidence: In general, the evidence for this mechanism in the reviewed studies is quite scarce. Colmer *et al* [63] study the investments of French manufacturing firms subject to the EU ETS and find a significant increase in investments caused by the carbon pricing policy. In particular, investments in less emission intensive processes and technologies are found

to increase, while there is no significant effect detected for investments on emissions detection or end-of-pipe emissions reductions. They further support their findings from the investment data by conducting a survey of French manufacturing firms. Firms which are participating in the EU ETS are found to be more likely to invest into improvements in the use of process heat as well as process optimisations. The causal impact of the investments on emissions is not assessed.

Only one study assesses the interaction between the policy and foreign direct investment. Their findings imply that, while foreign direct investment in China generally has an increasing effect on GHG emissions, this effect is reversed by the introduction of the pilot ETS policy [85]. Without the backing of further evidence this should however be treated with caution.

Some more descriptive evidence is provided by Runst and Thonipara [66] for the Swedish buildings sector. They find that heat pump sales substantially increase following a significant increase of the Swedish carbon tax rate from about US\$ 50 to above US\$ 120. During the same years, the residential per capita emissions decrease significantly. The authors point to an 'adjustment lag', which supports the assumption that emission reductions achieved via investments will take some time.

Conclusion: The scarce evidence described by the reviewed studies provides a weak indication that carbon pricing fosters investments. One study from Sweden points to the critical role of the carbon price level to incentivise investments. Again, the limitation in the available evidence is likely explained by this mechanism requiring time to unfold, while the reviewed studies are largely focused on the first few years after the policies were introduced. Further evidence would need to be collected to test this hypothesis. While we would expect the investment mechanism to be highly context dependent, the evidence does not allow to study the investment responses by different types of households and firms, across sectors, or financial conditions.

4.1.5. Hypothesis: carbon pricing spurs research and development to achieve emissions reductions

Besides investment in available technologies, the policy is expected to incentivise an uptake of research and development to find new solutions for emissions reductions [59, 67, 69, 70, 80, 81, 84, 86, 112, 113]. The success of these activities to develop scalable solutions for carbon intensive processes is not guaranteed and is expected to take time before resulting in emissions reductions [67].

Evidence: This mechanism is only studied for the Chinese ETS pilots among the studies we review. The evidence shows weak indications for increased

expenditure for research and development as well as for an increased number of issued patents. Early evidence also suggests that increased research activities have played a role in bringing emissions down.

Out of three studies assessing the expenditure, two find an increase [70, 86] (the latter assesses an index combining expenditure with further research and development indicators), while one study does not find a significant effect of the ETS pilots on the expenditure for research and development [67]. Yang *et al* [112] finds that also the governmental expenditure for research and development significantly increased with the implementation of the policy. It is, however, difficult to argue that governmental spending can be the result of a policy.

With respect to issued patents, Xu [69] find that the Chinese ETS pilots have a positive effect on the total number of issued patents. Dong *et al* [74] divide the patent data into 'green inventions' and other inventions (without a transparent definition for green inventions) and find that the ETS pilots specifically promoted 'green' innovation. This is partially supported by Chen *et al* [113], who find mixed results for different indices of low-carbon technology patents.

Xu [69] and Wang *et al* [70] further test, whether achieved emission reductions are caused by the increased innovation efforts using mediation analysis. Both studies find that the uptake in innovation is a causal mechanism towards emissions reductions. The studies assess data for the first seven and three years after the policy implementation, respectively. This either implies a very rapid success of the innovation mechanism or questions the reliability of the findings.

Conclusion: The reviewed evidence provides a weak signal of an uptake in research and development activities fostered by the Chinese ETS pilots. Only some of the studies find statistically significant effects for some measures of the research and development activities. Early assessments of the causality of this mechanism for emissions reductions imply a causal chain from carbon pricing via research and development leading to emissions reductions. The significance of this mechanism should be further substantiated with evidence from other carbon pricing schemes and studies of longer time periods. Cross-country comparisons could reveal how the heterogeneous research landscapes in different countries influence the research and development mechanism. The reviewed studies also provide no details which products or processes are subject to the research activities.

4.1.6. Hypothesis: emissions are reduced by reducing production

Instead of adjusting the production processes, firms and households could also avoid the costs induced by carbon pricing by scaling down their production or consumption [58, 59, 70, 77, 81, 84, 86, 88, 110]. The

carbon price induced cost may make the production of specific products unprofitable [77] or deteriorate their competitiveness with respect to products that are not subject to the policy [112], causing firms to reduce their production. If the costs are passed on to consumers, they may also adjust their consumption accordingly [110].

This mechanism is mainly expected in the manufacturing [77, 84] and energy [58, 59] sectors. As the demand for heating and transport are assumed to be inelastic, this mechanism is not assumed to significantly affect the buildings and transport sectors [91]. At least for the aviation sector, Heiaas [110] challenges the inelasticity assumption and instead assumes reduced demand for air travel once ticket prices are increased.

Reduction in production is a flexible response to policy signals and may be temporary until a more permanent solution is achieved via one of the other mechanisms with a longer time lag [84, 110]. Carbon induced costs are most significant for emission intensive firms, which are therefore expected to be the first to reduce production, potentially being replaced by less carbon intensive industries [69]. A reduction of production by firms subject to the policy may be replaced by firms that are not regulated by the same policy [59]. This mechanism is discussed in section 4.1.7 below.

The assumption of reduced production may also be reversed. As discussed above, the policy may foster the adoption of more efficient technologies. These in turn may have a positive impact on production [69, 88].

Evidence: The reviewed evidence does not suggest significant reductions in overall production levels. Measured by the gross domestic product (GDP), no evidence for reduced production levels is found for the Chinese ETS pilots [71, 75, 88, 89, 92], British Columbia carbon tax [93], or carbon taxes applied across European countries [94]. Only one study challenges the overall consistent evidence for China, finding some indication for a short-term reduction in GDP in the first year of the policy [114], while the significance of the finding (from a synthetic control design) is unclear.

Other studies instead proxy the overall output using data on employment levels. From significant reductions in employment caused by the Quebec ETS, Hanoteau and Talbot [84] conclude negative effects of the policy on production. The Chinese ETS pilots, on the other hand, are found to have a positive impact on employment levels [112]. Changes in employment levels are not necessarily an indication for changes in the level of output and should only be interpreted as suggestive evidence for a change in production.

Sectoral level estimates show that industrial output was not affected by carbon pricing, while other

sectors were triggered to reduce their production. Industrial output is measured in accordance with the GDP examined above. It is not found to be significantly reduced by the Chinese ETS pilots [88, 89] or the EU ETS [62]. Sector specific measures of economic activity, show reduced energy generation caused by the Chinese ETS pilots [68, 75, 79, 83], but not by the Tokyo ETS [87]. Descriptive evidence for the UK carbon price support shows a modest decline in electricity consumption of about 5% during the first few years of the policy [53]. The EU ETS is further found to cause a significant reduction in short-haul flights below 1000 km distance [90].

Heterogeneous responses in gasoline demand are found for the transport sector in British Columbia. While the carbon tax is found to reduce the demand in larger cities, more rural areas show no response to the carbon pricing policy [91]. This could be explained by more readily available alternative modes of mobility, such as public transport, cycling, or walking.

Reductions in electricity consumption, air travel, or gasoline demand cause emissions reductions as long as they are not replaced by other emission intensive practices.

Conclusion: Carbon pricing is not found to generally reduce production, but specific sectors react to the policy by scaling down their activities. The evidence does not reveal why the sectoral declines are not showing up in the larger aggregates. This could be related to measurement uncertainty or the size of the effect being too small compared to the aggregate. More interestingly, it might also be explained by shifts in economic activities, which are insufficiently studied. Declines in flights or car use may, for instance, be substituted by an increase in train travel. This should be further investigated by future research for a better understanding of the mechanism. The decline in specific modes of transport points toward a relevant condition for this mechanism to unfold. Urban car travel and short-haul flights may be substituted by other modes of transport, while car use in rural areas or long-distance flights are not as easily substitutable. Reductions in electricity use could be the result of a variety of behavioural changes and the reviewed evidence does not point to one specific explanation.

4.1.7. Hypothesis: carbon prices cause 'leakage'

Firms can also try to avoid policies by relocating their production and associated emissions to other jurisdictions or facilities not subject to the policy [54, 57–59, 63, 67, 68, 84, 95–97, 112, 115–117]. This phenomenon, known as leakage may be observed in different forms. Firms operating both within and outside the carbon price jurisdiction could relocate (parts of) their production to facilities outside the regulated area [63, 95, 97]. Leakage can also occur when actors within the carbon pricing jurisdiction

take the decision to reduce production, resulting in an increased import from or decreased exports to non-affected jurisdictions [62, 96, 97]. Even within the jurisdiction the policy may incentivise firms to reallocate their production, if some actors (e.g. based on the size of the facility) are exempted from the carbon price [61, 63].

The leakage mechanism is available in the short-run if spare production capacities [54, 95] and, in the case of the energy sector, transmission capacities [54] are available. It might be a temporary response to carbon pricing until other emission reduction mechanisms, which take longer to implement, become operational [59]. Some sectors are more prone to emission leakage than others [117]. In particular, the energy [57, 58] and industrial [96] production can be relocated. In the transport sector, leakage is limited to cross-border fuel shopping [91] and in the buildings sector the leakage mechanism is likely unavailable.

Emission leakage can offset achieved emissions reductions and potentially increase global emissions [63]. Counter to the leakage hypothesis, carbon pricing could also cause emissions reductions outside the treated jurisdiction, if enhanced procedures and technologies are adapted by those not subject to the policy or if emissions reductions outside the regulated area can be accounted for to lower carbon price expenses (off-sets) [67, 97, 115].

Evidence: Evidence on emission leakage is found for the Californian cap-and-trade scheme [95], for the RGGI [57–59], and for the UK carbon price support [53]. Studies on the EU ETS [61–63], Chinese ETS pilots [67, 68], Tokyo ETS, and Saitama ETS [97] do not show evidence for emission leakage. Firms that operate in California and also have plants outside of California are found to shift production from Californian plants to facilities not subject to the cap-and-trade policy, causing a reduction in emissions in California and an uptake outside of California [95]. For both the UK and the RGGI participating states, evidence shows that some of the reductions in electricity generation from coal and natural gas within the policy area are replaced by energy generation from outside the policy area [53, 57–59].

For the EU ETS, different lines of evidence are examined, with none pointing towards leakage. Wagner *et al* [61] and Colmer *et al* [63] examine emission leakage within the EU. As the policy entails exceptions, particularly, based on the size of the facility, emissions could be reallocated from larger to smaller facilities. Both studies find no evidence for within EU leakage in the French manufacturing sector. Colmer *et al* [63] furthermore finds no evidence for emission leakage via increased imports of emission-intensive intermediate products from outside the EU. French manufacturing firms are not found to increase their import volumes. Petrick and Wagner [62] examine whether emissions of German

export goods may be relocated by production outside the EU. The study finds no reduction in German manufacturing exports, but cautions the interpretation of the findings, as the studied data include export data to other EU countries, which are subject to the same policy. Chinese ETS pilots are not found to cause significant increases in electricity imports or increased power generation in neighbouring countries [68]. Also for other sectors, Yang *et al* [67] do not find any effects on increasing emissions in areas adjacent to the pilot regions. Gao *et al* [96] calculate production based and consumption based emissions for the pilot regions. The study finds slightly larger emissions reductions for production based emissions, but does not test whether the difference is statistically significant.

The total effectiveness of the policy beyond the regulated facilities depends on the relation of leaked emissions to the achieved emissions reductions. Evidence for California shows that the policy caused emissions increases outside the cap-and-trade area, which outweigh the achieved emissions reductions within California [95]. In the UK and RGGI states, the imported electricity had a lower emission intensity than the replaced (mostly coal) electricity. For Japan, the evidence even suggests a positive spill-over effect from the ETS policies in Tokyo and Saitama. Firms subject to one of the ETS policies are found to reduce their emissions not only in the facilities within the regulated area, but also in facilities that are not subject to the policy [97].

Conclusion: The emission leakage mechanism is found to play a role for some, but not all, carbon pricing schemes. Evidence for leakage is found for the UK and RGGI energy sectors and the Californian industry sector. The evidence from the UK and the RGGI states highlight a specificity of the energy sector, where leakage is facilitated by transmission capacities, but also limited to the available capacities for the energy import. In the industry sector import capacities are not limited by such explicit factors and transport capacities should usually be adjustable. Beyond that we do not identify clear patterns explaining the extent of leakage. While the cases of California, the UK, and the RGGI states indicate the relevance of the proximity and economic integration of regulated and non-regulated areas, this is contradicted by missing evidence for leakage in China between the ETS pilot regions and their neighbouring provinces. This should be studied further to resolve this puzzle and to identify which other context factors are relevant to trigger the leakage mechanism. This could inform policymakers how negative consequences of leakage may be avoided. Given that the studied leakage effects take place in a context of comparatively low carbon price levels, further evaluation is needed to understand to what extent higher carbon prices

intensify the leakage mechanism, undermining global emissions reductions.

4.2. Cognitive mechanisms

4.2.1. Hypothesis: attention to the carbon price triggers emissions reductions

The above mechanisms require firms and individuals to take action. It is hypothesised that the likelihood of these being triggered depends on the attention the carbon price attracts among different actors [100, 105, 118]. Prices for fossil fuels are commonly quite volatile, such that the effectiveness of a carbon price is argued to depend on the degree with which this price change is recognised by market participants [100, 105]. Only if the policy induced price changes receive the attention of the polluters, an emission reduction can be triggered. The attention mechanism is not expected to cause emissions reductions in and of itself. Instead, if the policy triggers the attention mechanism, this in turn may trigger the above emission reduction mechanisms. Only if it succeeds to spark at least one emission reduction mechanism, it may lead to emissions reductions.

Evidence: Three lines of evidence can be interpreted to support this hypothesis. First, the reaction to a carbon price significantly exceeds the response to other fuel price changes. Evidence from British Columbia shows that for both the transport [91, 100] and the buildings sector [101] the semi-elasticity of fuel demand is significantly higher for carbon price changes than for market price changes, indicating a specific salience of the policy induced price change.

Second, the introduction of a carbon price is found to cause an introduction effect unrelated to the size of the carbon price. This is based on a cross-country evaluation of carbon prices introduced at various price levels [102].

Lastly, Dechezleprêtre *et al* [99] and Cló *et al* [98] show that firms with abundant emission allowances reduce their emissions less than firms with a shortage of emissions allowances, even though the opportunity cost of an emitted ton of carbon dioxide is the same for the purchase or sale of an allowance. This may be explained by the higher awareness for the carbon price when purchasing an allowance compared to the forgone opportunity cost of selling an allowance at the same price.

Conclusion: The evidence provides some indication that the effectiveness of carbon pricing is related to the attention received by the actors. Further research is needed to better understand the relevance of this mechanism and potential implications for the communication of the policy. The reviewed evidence suggests that both households and firms are affected by the attention mechanism. The interaction of this cognitive mechanism with the emission reduction mechanisms needs to be studied further, to reveal how the

attention of any actor for the carbon pricing policy unleashes other mechanisms.

4.2.2. Hypothesis: emission reductions depend on anticipated carbon prices

Any reaction to a carbon pricing policy is assumed to be dependent on the expectations of future carbon prices [84, 105, 117]. The expectations of future carbon prices are triggered by the policy, which in turn may trigger emissions reduction mechanisms. This is particularly the case for mechanisms that require long-term planning, such as investment or research and development decisions [84]. If a carbon price generates expectations of permanently increasing fuel prices, this will be accounted for in the decision making [105]. This mechanism may, however, be reversed if firms expect to have an influence on the future stringency of the policy, such that lower abatement efforts today would lead to looser emission caps in future.

Evidence: There are two lines of evidence providing an indication of the relevance of expectations for emissions reductions. Murray and Maniloff [103] and Petrick and Wagner [62] find evidence for an emissions reduction effect already before the policy was implemented, while Pretis [104] and Erutku and Hildebrand [105] find lowered emission reduction efforts when expected tax increases did not materialise.

For both the EU ETS and the RGGI, the policy was announced respectively two and three years before coming into force. This resulted in significant emissions reductions in the affected sectors already before the carbon price was charged [62, 103]. Gao *et al* [96] and Cui *et al* [75] test for the same effect for the Chinese ETS pilots and do not find significant emissions reductions during the two years between the announcement and the implementation of the policy. The reviewed evidence provides no indication, why the anticipation mechanism works differently in the EU and US contexts compared to the Chinese case.

Revoked carbon tax increases were found to decrease the achieved emissions reductions in British Columbia. The policy was scheduled to regularly increase the tax rate by a fixed amount each year. This plan was revoked after the first four price raises and the tax was held constant between 2012 and 2018. Pretis [104] and Erutku and Hildebrand [105] find that the non-occurrence of the tax increase in 2012 coincided with a decreasing effectiveness of the policy and a rebound of emissions in the transport sector.

Conclusion: The limited evidence evaluated here, supports the hypothesis that carbon pricing policies trigger an expectation of future costs, which influences the emissions reductions achieved by the policy. The reviewed evidence provides no insights, which emission reduction mechanisms are triggered by the

anticipation mechanism. Further research should be assessed to better understand the carbon price expectations of different actors and how they interact with the mechanisms for emissions reductions. It should also be studied, why the anticipation mechanism was not found for the Chinese pilot ETS schemes.

5. Discussion

In this article we provide the first realist synthesis of the mechanisms behind carbon pricing policies. Carbon pricing is commonly formulated in mathematical terms, assuming an *a priori* relationship between prices and emissions [14, 18, 19]. In this study, we focus on the mechanisms substantiating this relationship, allowing us to form a better understanding of the context factors that shape policy effectiveness. We synthesise 177 hypotheses from 80 carbon pricing policy evaluations and identify nine main mechanisms of how carbon pricing works and a range of context factors, which make it more or less effective. We assess 293 pieces of empirical evidence to test the validity of each of the hypotheses across the contextual variations from 21 policy schemes and four emissions sectors. We provide a refined theory of the causal links between the application of carbon prices and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

Meta-analyses have established that carbon pricing effectively reduces greenhouse gas emissions, with varying and largely unexplained variations between schemes [8, 26]. How these emissions reductions come about has previously not been systematically assessed. While most of the mechanisms assessed here have been the subject of previous reviews, none of them had used a formalised synthesis method to derive hypotheses from the reviewed evidence to explain under what conditions and why the mechanisms unfold. Previous reviews on carbon pricing have covered fuel switching [17, 119], low-carbon technology adoption [15, 20, 21], investments [15, 119, 120], research and development [15, 20, 27, 119, 120], reduced production [21, 121], and leakage [122]), but have not attempted to systematically study how these mechanisms unfold in varying country and sector contexts.

In this study, we identify nine mechanisms triggered by carbon pricing policies that lead to emissions reductions. Table 3 summarises the evidence evaluated in this review and derives refined hypotheses on the relevance of different mechanisms for different sectors. It suggests differences in the ways in which emissions reductions are achieved across sector contexts. Fuel switching, for example, appears to be a viable mechanism mainly in the energy sector, where gas power plants which previously served as back-up can flexibly increase its operation time and replace higher emitting coal power plants given the

carbon price is high enough to reverse the cost incentives of the fuels. For the industry, transport, or buildings sectors, fuel switching is regularly dependent on the replacement of production facilities, vehicles, or heating systems, which prevents this mechanism from playing a major role in the short-term. The industry sector is instead observed to reduce emissions by improving its efficiency, while in the transport sector a switch to alternative modes of transport is observed, where feasible. The reviewed evidence also points to the relevance of the attention received by the policy and the anticipation of future carbon prices influencing the emissions reduction effect of the policy. The interaction of these mechanisms with other emissions reduction mechanisms should be studied further, as we limit ourselves in this review to studying the mechanisms in isolation, while in reality they should be assumed to interact extensively.

We acknowledge that the reviewed evidence is unevenly distributed and answers the question ‘under what conditions and why’ mechanisms unfold at different levels of detail. In particular, for mechanisms that are likely to unfold more gradually, the reviewed evidence is still insufficient to conclude whether and under what conditions these are triggered by the policy. Investments, research and development activities, or the adoption of new technologies are assumed to lead to emissions reductions, but this will not happen from one day to the next. Large part of the evidence reviewed here is derived from quasi-experimental study designs, which are well suited to study abrupt responses to an intervention, but provide fewer insights on gradual long-term changes. This likely explains why the reviewed evidence is more conclusive for those mechanisms that are triggered immediately than for those unfolding over longer time periods. Further evidence should be consulted to substantiate to what extent carbon pricing is able to unlock investment, research and the adoption of low-carbon technologies.

Concerning policy implications, this study suggests that it is important to account for potential differences in responses to carbon pricing across sectors and actors. Households, for instance, are in the short-run found to reduce carbon intensive modes of transport where alternatives are available. The replacement of heating appliances or cars, on the other hand, is rather a longer term strategy and could be supported by supplementary policies, if the reaction is meant to be accelerated. In the industry and energy sectors on the other hand, unused technical potentials for emissions reductions are unlocked by providing a cost incentive.

The reviewed evidence also indicates a crucial role of policy signalling. The attention received by the policy and the longer term expectations are found to influence the strength of the emission reduction response. Awareness of the emission duty and a clear

Table 3. Refined hypotheses on the relevance of different emissions reduction mechanisms by sector: The table summarises the above reviewed evidence on a sector level. Evidence that is not specific to a sector is not considered here. For each sector-mechanism combination the table states the amount of evidence considered. Quasi-experimental evidence is derived from difference-in-differences or regression discontinuity designs. Descriptive evidence is derived from data without any causal inference method. Cross-country evidence is derived by causal inference across a panel of countries. We develop refined hypotheses based on the reviewed evidence. These can be tested and further refined by future research. As longer-term evidence is under-represented in this review, the refined hypotheses focus on the mechanisms expected in the short-term.

Sector	Mechanism	Evidence		Refined Hypothesis
		Finding	Studies	
Energy	Fuel switching	Switching from coal to gas in UK, but not in EU or RGGI states	12 quasi experimental, 1 descriptive	Carbon pricing has a high potential for driving emissions reductions in the energy sector via fuel switching, due to regular access capacities. Reductions in energy production and leakage may additionally play a role, dependent on the local circumstances.
	Low-carbon technology adoption	Little evidence for the adoption of renewable or nuclear energy sources	3 quasi-experimental	
	Reduced production/consumption	Reduced energy production caused by Chinese ETS pilots, but not by Tokyo ETS	4 quasi-experimental	
	Leakage	Increased electricity imports by UK and RGGI states, but not by Chinese ETS pilot regions	5 quasi-experimental	
Industry	Efficiency improvements	Reduced emission intensity in EU industry sector	5 quasi-experimental	Carbon pricing in the industry sector mainly stimulates emissions reductions via increased efficiencies facilitated by investments into abatement technologies. Leakage is only relevant in specific cases. So far there is no evidence of low-carbon technology adoption.
	Investments	Increased investments in EU industry sector	1 quasi-experimental, 1 survey	
	Reduced production/consumption	No reductions of industrial output in China or EU	3 quasi-experimental	
	Leakage	Leakage found for California but not for the EU ETS	5 quasi-experimental	

(Continued.)

Table 3. (Continued.)

Sector	Mechanism	Evidence		Refined Hypothesis
		Finding	Studies	
Transport	Fuel switching	Switch to lower-carbon transport fuels across longer time horizon in Finland and Sweden	2 descriptive	In the consumption sectors, households react to carbon prices by reducing carbon intensive practices, where alternatives are available. Over longer time periods, vehicle and heating choices can further reduce emissions.
	Reduced production/consumption	Reduced urban car use (British Columbia) and short-haul flights (EU)	2 quasi-experimental	
Buildings	Fuel switching	Switch to lower-carbon heating fuels across longer time horizon in Sweden	1 descriptive	
	Low-carbon technology adoption	Uptake of heat pump installations in Sweden	1 descriptive	
	Attention	Across sectors, policy has a larger effect than explained by price change (EU, British Columbia, cross-country)	5 quasi-experimental, 1 cross-country panel	Actors across sectors react stronger to carbon prices than their stringency would imply, due to anticipated future prices and the attention received by the policy.
	Anticipation	Across sectors, actors anticipate future prices in emissions reaction (RGGI, EU, British Columbia; not in China)	6 quasi-experimental	

expectation of rising prices can intensify the policy response. This stresses the need for consistent policy planning and a clear communication of the governments intentions for climate change mitigation.

The realist synthesis could further be extended to more explicitly study the relevance of the carbon price level on each of the mechanisms. While it should be assumed that a higher carbon price leads to increased emissions reduction efforts, it may influence different mechanisms at different degrees. The studies reviewed here do not provide sufficient evidence to study the effect of the carbon price level in detail. The theory developed here could be used to update our assumptions of abatement costs [123–125] by refining the assumptions of the cost in relation to specific mechanisms and contexts. It should, however, be noted that the majority of studies in our sample assess carbon pricing schemes with average prices below US\$ 30 during the study period. With an increasing number of carbon pricing schemes with significantly higher prices, the evidence base should be strengthened to assess how the mechanisms unfold with higher carbon prices.

Other context factors that are not yet sufficiently studied are external shocks and supplementary policies that may support or obstruct the effect of carbon pricing. In the reviewed cases, we note the coincidence of a number of carbon pricing schemes with an economic recession (EU ETS, RGGI, and carbon taxes in Sweden, Finland, and British Columbia) [62, 64, 65, 77, 100, 103] or natural disaster (Tokyo and Saitama ETS) [116]. The reviewed studies provide little evidence how these events have interfered with the carbon pricing mechanisms. Similarly, there is a growing interest in the synergies and conflict between policy instruments [2, 126–128], but our sample provides little insights in the interaction of carbon pricing with other policies. The theory developed here needs to be further refined taking into account these context factors.

Many of the evidence gaps identified here could likely be filled by expanding the amount of considered evidence and by more comprehensively integrating heterogeneous lines of evidence from qualitative studies, surveys, descriptive studies, etc. The 80 studies reviewed here provide a rich set of evidence on a range of CMO configurations, while others are not (sufficiently) studied. The realist synthesis approach encourages to iteratively search for and review evidence, identify new hypotheses during the synthesis, and test these by reviewing further lines of evidence. Considering the massive amount of potentially relevant evidence [23], this may easily grow into an infinite review project. Realist synthesis therefore challenges the reviewer to find the right balance between the comprehensiveness of the review and the feasibility of the project. Given the many unanswered hypotheses that could be derived from the synthesis provided here, we find it difficult to conclude the project at this

stage, but are positive about the contribution this first realist synthesis can bring to enhance our understanding of the mechanisms behind carbon pricing. The framework of contexts and mechanisms developed here may be used to further refine the evidence-based theory by integrating further lines of evidence.

While additional searches for evidence would be expected to fill some of the identified gaps, systematic reviews of carbon pricing policies commonly find that large amounts of implemented policies are understudied [8, 26, 27]. We here review evidence on 21 carbon pricing schemes, less than a third of all the schemes implemented around the world [12]. For a more comprehensive assessment of context factors, primary research should widen their focus and more intensively study the effects of policies that have yet received too little attention. Similarly, primary research should intensify research on mechanisms that have, yet, received too little attention, such as low-carbon technology scaling, investments, research and development activities, and cognitive mechanisms.

With this realist synthesis we aim to pave the way for more configurative systematic reviews in the field of climate policy evaluation. However, we need to critically reflect to what extent this study meets the high standards for a systematic review. Following a predefined method for systematically collecting, extracting, synthesising primary evidence we significantly reduce the subjectivity of our analysis. We conduct a comprehensive search, set out clear criteria for the inclusion of studies, and provide a transparent account of studies excluded or included in the review. The systematic extraction and clustering of hypotheses and evidence increases the objectivity of the considered data. While some subjectivity remains in the definition of the mechanisms and contexts by which the data is reported, the systematic collection and transparent method ensure that the evidence is not reported selectively or that major elements are overlooked. This provides a clear advantage over traditional literature reviews, which usually provide no account of how the reviewed literature is selected and apply no review method to structure the evidence. The wide range of considered evidence reviewed here, for instance, reveals that there is no simple answer whether carbon pricing triggers fuel switching or leakage, but that heterogeneous policy responses are observed depending on the context, requiring a careful review of various lines of (at times contradicting) evidence. The realist review method, however, unlike other systematic review methods [129, 130], does not allow for a comprehensive assessment of all evidence that could be relevant to answer the research question. Here, we only review the evidence provided in quantitative ex-post policy evaluations on the effectiveness of carbon pricing.

Realist synthesis is a promising tool to facilitate evidence-based policymaking. It provides nuanced

insights to understand how and under what conditions a climate policy measure works, forming a sound knowledge base to inform decision makers. Here, we provide a starting point for understanding which mechanisms are triggered by carbon pricing policies in different contexts. This should further be refined, integrating the wide array of relevant evidence to derive a robust theory of how the policy works. The assessment framework developed here can be adapted to assess other climate policies and be extended to study further policy outcomes. Policymakers require sound knowledge of how climate policies can achieve substantial emissions reductions and how they affect other policy aims. We need to make the best use of the available evidence to understand what climate policies work, under what conditions, and why, to stand a chance of achieving emissions reductions at a pace required to stay within the 1.5° C or 2° C warming limits [131].

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15295817>.

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